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Biogas Production from Animal Manure

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Table of Contents

List of Table	III
List of Figure	IV
Abstract	V
Chapter one	1
Introduction	1
1.1. Background	1
1.2. Statement of problem	3
1.3. Objectives	3
1.3.1. General Objectives	3
1.3.2. Specific Objectives	3
1.4. Scope and limitation	3
Chapter two	5
2. Literature Review	5
2.1. Biogas production process	5
2.1.1. Hydrolysis	5
2.1.2. Acidogenesis	5
2.1.3. Acetogenesis	6
2.1.4. Methanogenesis	6
2.2. Factors Affecting Biogas Production	6
2.3. Biogas Slurry	10
2.4. Characteristics of Biogas	12
2.5. Solid Waste Management	12
2.5.1. Nature of the Waste	13
2.5.2. Potential Sites for Manure Collection	13
2.6. Types of generator	13
Chapter Three	18
3. Material and Methodology	18
3.1. Materials	18
3.2. Chemicals	18
3.3. Production methodology	18
Chapter Four	21

4. Result and Discussion	21
4.1. Result	21
4.2. Discussion	21
Chapter Five	22
5. Conclusion and Recommendation	22
5.1. Conclusion	22
5.2. Recommendation	22
Reference	I

List of Table

Table 2.1: C/N ratio of different raw materials	11
Table 2.2: Features of biogas	12

List of Figure

Figure2- 1: Floating drum	15
Figure 2- 2: Floating drum	16
figure 2- 3: PFD of biogas	17
Figure 3- 1: Experiment 1 Biogas production prototype	19
Figure 3- 2: Experiment 2 biogas production prototype	19
Figure 3- 3: Experiment 3 Biogas production prototype	20

Abstract

Biogas production is a well-established process for energy generation, nutrient recovery, and vaporization of organic residues. Typically, the biogas is composed of methane, carbon dioxide, and other impurities. The removal or transformation of carbon dioxide (biogas upgrading) and the purification from other contaminants (biogas cleaning) are essential for increasing the calorific value of biogas. Therefore, the new trends in exploiting biogas as an alternative to natural gas, the recent renewable energy demands and the interest in placing biogas sector as a keystone in circular bio-based economy societies paved the way for establishing new technologies for upgrading the biogas quality.

We conducted 4 experiments using different materials but we didn't get any flame but simultaneously we conducted an experiment with the first experiment in 1 litter. At that time our plastic became highly expanded so we expect it becomes a gas. We didn't get any flame Because of different factors such as:-

The temperature in the biogas plant should be constant, the size of tube (should be small to transfer a gas at a high pressure), mixing may affect our gas production, the manure condition (fresh, dried and recent, old).

Chapter one

Introduction

1.1. Background

Biogas plants have been accepted by now in the country as a device for improving the quality of the life of the people. They help in recycling of the cattle wastes and produce both fuel and manure from the same quantity of dung. At present peoples in rural areas are started to use biogas in the country. The majority of these biogas plants use cattle dung as the feed stock. At the same time there are efforts to also use alternative feed stocks like human excreta, and also other agricultural wastes, water hyacinth etc. The safe disposal of night—soil/human excreta is of major consideration for any sanitary programs and one of them can be through feeding It into the biogas digesters. It is agreed that the use of the gas from the night soil will be considered taboo by the majority of our people.

Biogas is a production made from the fermentation of biodegradable materials such as sewage, manure, waste water from livestock farms and industrial plants. “Biogas” is produced by the anaerobic digestion of organic substances with anaerobic bacteria in the absence of oxygen (anaerobic condition). Microbial-controlled production of biogas is an important part of the global carbon cycle. Every year, natural bio-degradation of organic matter under anaerobic conditions is estimated to release 590–800 million tons of methane into the atmosphere (Michael R. Templeton , Tom Bond). Biogas recovery systems exploit these biochemical processes to decompose various types of biomass, with the liberated biogas potentially providing an energy source. There is a distinction between anthropogenic anaerobic processes which recover the energy within biogas and those which do not. Examples of the first category are bio-reactors designed specifically for substrates, including sewage, agricultural, industrial and municipal waste, containing a high proportion of anaerobically-degradable biomass.

In developing countries the expansion of biogas recovery systems has been based upon small-scale reactors designed for digestion of cattle, pig and poultry excreta. Meanwhile, landfill sites and municipal waste water treatment plants where anaerobic processes produce biogas which is released into the atmosphere, either before or after combustion, belong to the second category. Biogas contains 50–70% methane and 30–50% carbon dioxide, depending on the substrate

(Ludwig Sasse, 1988) as well as small amounts of other gases including hydrogen sulphide. Methane is the component chiefly responsible for a typical calorific value of 21–24 MJ/m³ (Dimpl, 2010) or around 6kWh/m³. Biogas is often used for cooking, heating, lighting or electricity generation.

Larger plants can feed biogas into gas supply networks. The activities of at least three bacterial communities are required by the biochemical chain which releases methane. Firstly, during hydrolysis, extra cellular enzymes degrade complex carbohydrates, proteins and lipids into their constituent units. Next is acidogenesis (or fermentation) where hydrolysis products are converted to acetic acid, hydrogen and carbon dioxide. The facultative bacteria mediating these reactions exhaust residual oxygen in the digester, thus producing suitable conditions for the final step: methanogenesis, where obligate anaerobic bacteria control methane production from acidogenesis products. Anaerobic digesters are typically designed to operate in the mesophilic (20–40 °C) or thermophilic (above 40 °C) temperature zones. Sludge produced from the anaerobic digestion of liquid biomass is often used as a fertilizer.

Biogas recovery technologies have been failures in many developing countries, with low rates of technology transfer and longevity and a reputation for being difficult to operate and maintain. Thus the objectives of this review were to identify the factors underlying successful and unsuccessful operation of domestic biogas plants and to investigate the future challenges, which, once overcome, would enable sustained expansion of bio gas technology. Biogas digester is any structure that converts organic material (waste) into energy in the absence of oxygen. Various materials and geometric configuration have been used for the design of biogas digester system. Examples of the geometric configuration are horizontal, spherical, and cylindrical and dome shape. Examples of common materials used are brick, cements, fiber glass for the dome shape and metal (stainless steel and mild steel). The disadvantages and advantages of the anaerobic treatment of an organic waste as compared to aerobic digestion stem directly from the slow growth rate of methanogens. Slow growth rates require high retention time for adequate waste stabilization to occur.

1.2. Statement of problem

Because of the population explosion and related energy demand of deforestation level due to the over use of fuel wood by the felling of trees and reduction of forest, are higher than forestation efforts they have resulted to environmental degradation.

Another major cause of the environmental degradation, which has become the greatest threat to the health of the environment and the economy of the under developed worlds, and most especially the developing and the developed worlds, is the use of fossil fuels. These fossil fuels are non-renewable, although the major source of the energy and income of the economy of many countries such as Nigeria. But with the discovery and utilization of biogas, which is a gaseous fuel obtained from biomass by the process of anaerobic digestion, most problems (e.g. Air, land, water pollution) and associated with the fossil fuel, are being resolved.

1.3. Objectives

1.3.1. General Objectives

The main objective of the project is to design biogas digester for production of biogas from animal manure and café waste at laboratory scale.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this project are to;

- To investigate the production of biogas from animal manure and café waste
- Demonstrate the effectiveness of the anaerobic digester as a cost effective means of waste minimization and energy production.
- Describe and explain design criteria for optimal performance.
- To study the biogas yield and its sufficiency for meeting the fuel requirement if required.

1.4. Scope and limitation

Limitations of Biogas Technology

a. The Impact of Methane on the Climate

Human activities such as cattle farming, rice farming and the accumulation of waste on large waste disposal sites, etc., are thought to have caused a doubling of the atmospheric concentration of methane to the present level of 1.7 ppm. This does not, as such, have any effect on human health. However, as methane is part of the chemical processes in the

atmosphere and is also a powerful greenhouse gas (about 22 times as powerful as carbon dioxide, CO₂), the gas is a contributor to the greenhouse effect. Methane has thus contributed about 20% to the total increase in the greenhouse effect caused by human activities. If the greenhouse effect results in an increasing temperature rise on our planet, there is a risk that the large areas of tundra currently under permafrost will slowly thaw, which will result in the release of huge quantities of methane when organic materials are gradually decomposed. This will obviously further exacerbate the greenhouse effect. Methane in large quantities also destroys ozone. Rising methane emissions can therefore have unfortunate consequences for the ozone layer that helps protect the Earth against the harmful ultraviolet radiation from the sun.

b. Few Technological Advancements

An unfortunate disadvantage of biogas today is that the systems used in the production of biogas are not efficient. There are no new technologies yet to simplify the process and make it abundant and low cost. This means large scale production to supply for a large population is still not possible. Although the biogas plants available today are able to meet some energy needs, many governments are not willing to invest in the sector.

c. Contains Impurities

After refinement and compression, biogas still contains impurities. If the generated bio-fuel was utilized to power automobiles, it can corrode the metal parts of the engine. This corrosion would lead to increased maintenance costs. The gaseous mix is much more suitable for kitchen stoves, water boilers, and lamps.

d. Effect of Temperature on Biogas Production

Like other renewable energy sources (e.g. solar, wind) biogas generation is also affected by the weather. The optimal temperature bacteria need to digest waste is around 37°C. In cold climates, digesters require heat energy to maintain a constant biogas supply.

e. Less Suitable For Dense Metropolitan Areas

Another biogas disadvantage is that industrial biogas plants only makes sense where raw materials are in plentiful supply (food waste, manure). For this reason, biogas generation is much more suitable for rural and suburban areas.

Chapter two

2. Literature Review

2.1. Biogas production process

Biogas is produced when bacteria digest organic matter (biomass) in the absence of oxygen. This process is called anaerobic digestion. It occurs naturally anywhere from the within the digestive system to the depth of effluent ponds and can be reproduced artificially in engineered containers called digesters. The whole biogas-process can be divided into three steps: hydrolysis, acidification, and methane formation. Many microorganisms take part in this complex transformation with the main role given to 3 types of methane-producing bacteria.

2.1.1. Hydrolysis

Biomass is normally comprised of large organic polymers proteins, fats and carbohydrates. These are broken down into smaller molecules such as amino acids, fatty acids, and simple sugars. It is the essential first step in anaerobic fermentation; fermentative bacteria hydrolyze the complex organic matter into soluble molecules. Some of the products of hydrolysis, including hydrogen and acetate may be used by methanogens later in the anaerobic digestion process. Majority of the molecules, which are still relatively large, must be further broken down in the process of abiogenesis so that they may be used to create methane.

2.1.2. Acidogenesis

Acidogenesis is the next step of anaerobic digestion where acidogenic microorganisms further break down the biomass and organic products after hydrolysis. These fermentative bacteria produce an acidic environment in the digestive tank while creating ammonia, H₂, CO₂, H₂S, shorter volatile fatty acids and organic acids, as well as trace amounts of other byproducts. The principal acids produced are acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid etc. Then decomposition is made by acid-forming bacteria. Separate molecules penetrate into bacteria cells where further transformation takes place. This process is partially accompanied by anaerobic bacteria that consume rest of oxygen hence providing suitable anaerobic environment for methane bacteria. The step is called Acidogenesis.

(Acetic acid)

(Butyric acid)

(Propionic acid)

2.1.3. Acetogenesis

In general, acetogenesis is the creation of acetate, a derivative of acetic acid, from carbon and energy sources by acetogens. These microorganisms catabolize many of the products created in acidogenesis into acetic acid, CO_2 and H_2 . Acetogens break down the biomass to a point to which methanogens can utilize much of the remaining material to create methane. For vital functions of these bacteria that consume hydrogen, stable temperature mode is very important.

2.1.4. Methanogenesis

Methanogenesis constitutes the final stage of anaerobic digestion in which methanogens create methane from the final products of acetogenesis as well as from some of the intermediate products from hydrolysis and acidogenesis. There are two general pathways involving the use of acetic acid and carbon dioxide, the two main products of the first three steps of anaerobic digestion, to create methane in methanogenesis:

While CO_2 can be converted into methane and water through the reaction, the main mechanism to create methane in methanogenesis is the path involving acetic acid. This stage leads to generation of methane and CO_2 , the two main products of anaerobic digestion.

2.2. Factors Affecting Biogas Production

Factors that Facilitate or Hinder Anaerobic Digestion

There are a number of factors that hinder or facilitate anaerobic digestion. These factors are:

- Temperature

- Carbon/Nitrogen Ratio
- PH Value
- Dilution and Consistency of Inputs
- Volatile Solids
- Loading rate
- Retention time
- Toxicity
- Location
- Inhibiting factors
- Agitation/mixing

Let us examine each factor in turn and how it affects gas production

Temperature:

The methanogens are inactive in extreme high and low temperatures. The Optimum temperature for these bacteria is 35° C. When the ambient temperature goes down to 10° C, gas production virtually stops. To increase gas production during the cold season, one can place a haystack on top of the digester in order to provide proper insulation. When the ambient temperature is 30°C or less, the average temperature within the dome remains 4° C above the ambient temperature. The process of bio-methanation is very sensitive to changes in temperature. The degree of sensitivity, in turn, is dependent on the temperature range. Brief fluctuations not exceeding $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C/h}$ do not inhibit the process of fermentation. The temperature fluctuations between day and night are not a great problem for plants built underground, since the temperature of the earth below a depth of one meter is practically constant.

Temperature choice and control are critical to the development of anaerobic digestion process, having a strong influence over the quality and quantity of biogas production. The microorganisms participating in the process of anaerobic digestion (especially methanogenic ones),

- Cryophiles (Psychrophiles), operating at temperatures from 12 to 24°C, digestion characteristic area under cryophilic regime;
- Mesophiles, operating at temperatures between 22-40°C, characteristic area for mesophilic regime digestion;

- Thermophiles, operating at temperatures between 50 – 60°C, characteristic area for thermophilic regime digestion (VINTILĂ, T., NIKOLIĆ, V., [14])

Carbon/Nitrogen Ratio:

The relationship between the amount of carbon and nitrogen present in organic materials is expressed in terms of the Carbon/Nitrogen (C/N) ratio. Microorganisms need both nitrogen and carbon for assimilation into their cell structures. A C/N ratio ranging from 20 to 30 is considered optimum for anaerobic digestion. If the C/N ratio is very high, the nitrogen will be consumed rapidly by the bacteria or methanogens and will no longer react on the leftover carbon content of the material. As a result, gas production will be low.

On the other hand, if the C/N ratio is very low, nitrogen will accumulate in the form of ammonia (NH₄). This will increase the pH value of the content in the digester, thus producing a toxic effect on the methanogen population. Therefore the C/N ratio of the substrate used in a biogas plant is important. Cattle, pig and poultry manures have a good C/N ratio.

pH value

The optimum biogas production is achieved when the pH value of input mixture in the digester is between 6 and 7. The pH in a biogas digester is also a function of the retention time. In the initial period of fermentation, as large amounts of organic acids are produced by acid forming bacteria, the pH inside the digester can decrease to below 5. This can inhibit or even stop the digestion or fermentation process.

Methanogenic bacteria are very sensitive to pH and do not thrive below a value of 6.5. Later, as the digestion process continues, concentration of NH₄ increases due to digestion of nitrogen which can increase the pH value to above 8. When the methane production level is stabilized, the pH range remains buffered between 7.2 -8.2.

Loading Rate

This refers to the amount of substrate or raw materials fed in the digester per day. If the plant is overfed, acids will accumulate and methane production will be inhibited. Similarly, if the plant is underfed, the gas production will be low.

Retention Time:

Is the time for which the biodegradable matter remains inside the reactor? HRT is influenced by the temperature inside the digester, the type of the feedstock and the technologies applied. Too short retention time might leave the bacteria getting washed out of the digester without they getting multiplied thus leaving the digester coming to standstill state and longer retention time would increase the volume of the reactor. Thus in order to reduce the retention time and reactor volume, the optimum loading rate is to be maintained for optimizing the methane gas generation. 2-3 weeks of time is considered optimum for lignocellulose material to degrade and generate biogas(IJRASET 2022).The theoretical retention time is calculated by dividing the average slurry holding volume of the digester by the volume of the substrate added daily. Depending on the vessel geometry and the means of mixing, the effective retention time may vary widely for the individual substrate constituents.

Volatile Solids:

Volatile solids are the part of the total solids contents of the substrate that can be converted into biogas. Biomass that is completely dried and then heated to about 550° C, will gasify. The weight of the dried biomass minus the weight of the remaining ash after gasification will be the weight of the volatile solids. The biogas production potential of different organic materials can also be calculated on the basis of their volatile solid content.

Dilution and Consistency of Inputs

Most biogas plants are designed for a total solids content of about 8%. A change of this ratio affects the proper functioning of the plant. Before feeding the digester, the excreta, especially fresh cattle dung, should be mixed with water at the ratio of 1:1, that is, same volume of water for a given volume of dung. However, if the dung is in a dry form, one should increase the quantity of water accordingly in order to arrive at the desired consistency of the substrate. For example, the ratio could vary from 1:1.25 to even 1:2). You should ensure that the dilution maintains a total solid content of 7 to 10%. If the dung is too diluted or too thick, this will lower gas production. This is because in the case of over diluted dung, the solid particles tend to settle down into the digester. While in the case of thick dung, the particles impede the flow of gas formed at the lower part of digester. There is also a higher risk of scum formation at the top of the slurry layer if the mixture is too thick.

Location

To increase the temperature of the substrate, sunny locations (i.e. away from trees or shade) are good locations for biogas generators. As a precaution for (unintended) leaching, generators should be situated at least 30m away from any water source or stream. No permanent structures or through ways should be built on the ground above a generator.

Inhibiting factors

The presence of heavy metals, antibiotics and detergents in the slurry can inhibit the biogas production process. Any addition of these to the digester should be avoided. Anything which is not biodegradable should not be added to the digester since it will take up valuable space and could lead to a blockage. It would seem that anal cleansing material (including water and paper) can be added to the digester whilst keeping in mind that the ideal solid:liquid ratio of 1:1 should be adhered to where possible.

Agitation/mixing

Mixing of the slurry can increase gas production by ensuring an even distribution of bacteria and fresh substrate. The large scale industrial generators are often fitted with motor-driven rotating paddles whilst smaller agricultural ones are mixed with long poles by hand. There is little information on the optimum frequency of mixing in human waste fed digesters but the gas production increases dramatically when mixing is undertaken (slowly and perhaps once a day or once a week). Different time intervals between mixes should be tried to identify the optimum level for any specific generator.

2.3. Biogas Slurry

This is what comes out through the outlet chamber after methanogenic bacteria act upon the substrate inside the digester. After extraction of biogas (energy), the slurry (also known as effluent) comes out of the digester as a by-product of the anaerobic digestion system. It is almost pathogen-free stabilized manure that can be used to maintain soil fertility and enhance crop production. Slurry is found in the following different forms inside the digester:

- A light rather solid fraction, mainly fibrous material, which float to the top forming scum;
- A very liquid and watery fraction which remains in the middle layer of the digester;
- A viscous fraction below which is the real slurry or sludge; and heavy solid, mainly sand and soils that deposit at the bottom. When the feed materials or substrate are homogenous,

there is less separation in the slurry. If you want to achieve homogeneous slurry, you should use the appropriate ratio of urine, water and excrement and mix the slurry intensively before feeding the digester.

When a biogas plant is underfed the gas production will be low; in this case, the pressure of the gas might not be sufficient to fully displace the slurry in the outlet chamber. It is important to design the plant keeping hydrostatic pressure higher at the inlet tank than the outlet tank. The hydrostatic pressure from slurry in the inlet and outlet tanks will pressurize the biogas accumulated in the dome. If too much material is fed into the digester and the volume of gas is consumed, the slurry may enter the gas pipe and to the appliances. When fully digested, the slurry from a biogas plant is odorless and does not attract insects or flies

Table 2.1: C/N ratio of different raw materials

Sample	Raw Materials	C/N Ratio
1.	Duck dung	8
2.	Human excreta	8
3.	Chicken dung	10
4.	Goat dung	12
5.	Pig dung	18
6.	Sheep dung	19
7.	Cow dung/ Buffalo dung	24
8.	Water hyacinth	25
9.	Elephant dung	43
10.	Straw (maize)	60
11.	Straw (rice)	70
12.	Straw (wheat)	90

	Saw dust	above 200
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2.4. Characteristics of Biogas

Biogas is about 20% lighter than air has an ignition temperature in range of 650 to 750 ° which is odorless & colorless gas that burns with blue flame similar to LPG gas. Its caloric value is 20 Mega Joules (MJ) /m³ and it usually burns with 60 % efficiency in a conventional biogas stove. This gas is useful as fuel to substitute firewood, cow-dung, petrol, LPG, diesel, & electricity, depending on the nature of the task, and local supply conditions and constraints.

The basic properties of biogas are:

- The change in volume of biogas is a function of temperature and pressure.
- The change in caloric value is given as a function of temperature, pressure and water content.
- The change in water vapor is as a function of temperature and pressure.

The general features of biogas are given as follows.

Table 2.2: Features of biogas

Energy content	6-6.5kW/m ³
Fuel equivalent	0.6-0.651 oil/m ³ biogas
Explosion limits	6-12% biogas in air
Ignition temperature	650-750°C
Critical pressure	75-89bar
Critical temperature	-82.5 °C
Normal density	1.2kg/ m ³
Smell	Bad eggs

2.5. Solid Waste Management

The undigested human waste with water is hazardous to public health and causes environmental pollution. Recycling and reuse of human excreta for biogas generation is an important way to get

rid of health hazards. Biogas technology improves the hygiene through the reduction of pathogens, worm eggs and flies. It was reported that “...anaerobic digestion in a digester will reduce BOD and TSS by 80-90%. Odor is virtually eliminated. The digester will have minimal effect on the nutrient content of the digested manure. Pathogen reduction is greater than 99% in a 20 day HRT mesophilic digester (100°F). Half or more of the organic nitrogen (Org-N) is mineralized to ammonia (NH₃-N). A small amount of the P and K will settle as sludge in most digesters.” [9]

Septic tanks are basically clarifiers and biological treatment systems that settle solids and rely on anaerobic or facultative microorganisms to provide biodegradation of organic wastes. EPA states that septic tanks decompose up to 50% of solids contained in the tank. Also septic tanks can't remove pathogens. Septic tanks decompose only 50% solids and pathogens cannot be removed at all. In biogas digesters the human waste is separated from the excess water and treated separately to ensure efficient treatment of the pathogens, BOD and TSS. Therefore biogas plants combined with the septic tanks increases the efficiency of the waste treatment system.

2.5.1. Nature of the Waste

The choice and performance of the digester is dependent on the nature of the feed stock. So one of the requirements for selection of suitable digester type is based on nature of wastes or feed stock.

2.5.2. Potential Sites for Manure Collection

Amount and nature of the waste has been considered for the sites selection near the gas consumption area. Space availability is one of major factor before starting any factory so we must select appropriate site for our system.

2.6. Types of generator

There are a number of designs/types of generator – the 3 most commonly used are (1) fixed-dome, (2) floating-drum and (3) balloon. Although the designs differ in detail each has 3 common parts which will be detailed in terms of design and construction for each type of generator:

- a. **Digester**– where biomass (slurry) is stored and broken down by bacteria to produce biogas

- b. **Biogas holder** – an area where the biogas is stored under pressure and can be tapped off (could be part of the digester).
- c. **Displacement tank/Slurry overflow** – method of removing fully digested slurry and prevention of over pressurization of biogas. Regardless of the type of generator there are some key parameters which need to be adhered to in order to ensure a good design.

Fixed-dome digester

Over-view waste matter is fed into the digester where it collects and is broken down, producing biogas which is stored in the gas holder part of the hemispherical digester; as the pressure of the biogas increases the more the volume of slurry which is displaced into the displacement tank. Excess slurry from the displacement tank will be removed, dried or composted and used for fertilizer or will overflow into a sewage outlet or slurry/composting bed. Biogas is removed from the gas holder and can be used for cooking, lighting and heating (as detailed). When the gas is used some of the slurry moves back from the displacement tank into the digester causing mixing. The fixed-dome generator is commonly known as the ‘Chinese’ design and can be used in small scale (household) or larger scale (community) systems.

Construction consists of an underground digester (usually flat/bowled base with a hemispherical top) covered with earth up to the top of the gas holder so as to counteract the gas pressure. Plastic pipes or masonry tunnels provide the inlet/outlet for the digester. Bricks and mortar are used to create the structure, the inside of which must be rendered and coated in a waterproof and gas-proof coating.

Benefits of fixed-dome generators include:

- simple design
- simple maintenance (no moving parts, no potential of rusting)
- long life (20 years+) o lower set-up costs

Disadvantages of fixed-dome generators include:

- fluctuating gas pressure
- Potential for leaks in mortar if not well constructed.

Figure2- 1: Floating drum

Floating-drum

Over-view As with fixed-drum generators the construction consists of an underground masonry digester (often cylindrical in shape). The gas storage area consists of an upturned enclosed steel structure (drum) which floats in a water jacket which surrounds the opening of the digester (or on the slurry itself). Biogas is tapped off from the top of the steel drum and used for cooking, lighting, etc. As the gas is produced and the gas pressure increases the steel drum floats higher in the water jacket – when the gas is used and the gas pressure drops the weight of the drum forces it to float lower. The floating-drum generator is known as the ‘Indian’ design and are widely used for small scale (household) size systems.

Benefits of floating-drum generators include:

- Constant gas pressure
- Can see how much gas had collected clearly (by height of drum)

Disadvantages of floating drum generators include:

- Corrosion problems with steel
- Expense of steel drum
- Complex construction due to moving parts
- Water jacket MUST be kept topped up to provide the gas seal.

Figure 2-2: Floating drum

Balloon

Over-view The balloon generator uses a flexible plastic bladder as the combined digester and gas holder. In a similar way to the previous 2 designs the inlet and outlet are situated at opposite ends of the balloon, which allows for the slurry to be digested and produce gas as it moves along inside the structure. Rocks or weights can be added to the top of the balloon to increase the gas pressure – the gas is tapped off from the top of the balloon.

Benefits of floating-drum generators include:

- Simple
- Quick to construct
- Transportable
- Low cost/standardized construction
- Shallow – suitable for high water table

Disadvantages of floating drum generators include:

- Variable gas pressure
- Easily damaged/not weather resistant
- Not structurally stable/fixed
- Short working life
- Difficult to clean

Figure 2- 3: Balloon digester

figure2- 3: PFD of biogas

Chapter Three

3. Material and Methodology

3.1. Materials

The following materials were used to produce biogas in laboratory.

- Analytical balance
- measuring cylinders
- Two 5l plastic bottles
- Two plastic glucose tube
- Animal dung
- Kitchen waste

3.2. Chemicals

- Water
- Glue

3.3. Production methodology

Two experimental studies were conducted using different raw materials.

Experiment 1

- i. A 10 liters plastic jar with its cap was prepared.
- ii. The animal dung was collected from the field.
- iii. A plastic tube was installed on the cap of the bottle.
- iv. Valve and a ball as gas holder is installed in the end of tube.
- v. 3.5 kg of cow dung was mixed with 3.5-liter water and around 3 liter was left for gas storage.
- vi. Then the bottle was placed at room temperature until the gas production start.

Figure 3- 1: Experiment 1 Biogas production prototype

Experiment 2

1. A 5 liters' transparent plastic bottle with its cap was prepared.
2. The animal dung was collected from the field.
3. A plastic glucose tube having a valve was installed on the cap of the bottle.
4. 1.5 kg of cow dung was mixed with 1.5-liter water and around 2 liter was left for gas storage.
5. Then the bottle was placed at room temperature until the gas production start.

Figure 3- 2: Experiment 2 biogas production prototype

Experiment 3

- i. A 5 liters' transparent plastic bottle with its cap was prepared.
- ii. The animal dung was collected from the field.
- iii. A plastic glucose tube having a valve was installed on the cap of the bottle.
- iv. 1.5 kg of cow dung was mixed with 1.5-liter water and around 2 liter was left for gas storage.
- v. Then the bottle was placed at room temperature until the gas production start.

Figure 3- 3: Experiment 3 Biogas production prototype

Experiment 4

- i. A '1 liters' transparent plastic bottle with its cap was prepared.
- ii. The animal dung was collected from the field.
- iii. A plastic glucose tube having a valve was installed on the cap of the bottle.
- iv. 600 g of cow dung was mixed with 600 milliliter water and around 800 milliliter was left for gas storage.
- v. Then the bottle was placed at room temperature until the gas production star

Chapter Four

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Result

After conducting 4 experiments we didn't get any flame but our simultaneous experiment with the first one using a 1 liter plastic bottle. The bottle expands too much and on the first experiment we get a color change on the water tube. So we expect it may be a gas.

4.2. Discussion

From a result we say that our experiment one may produce a gas if the tube becomes small glucose tube since it require a pressure to pass through a tube to be burned.in our experiment 2 we used an old animal dung which can affect our production of gas .generally from all of our experiment we expect that the freshness of cow dung, temperature and sizing of tube could affected our product.

Chapter Five

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1. Conclusion

In this paper we were trying to show our project in Hawassa university chemical engineering department process stream laboratory that was production of biogas from cow dung. four experiment were conducted in this project .in the experiment 1, we see a color change in the water tube but not production of flame because of the size of tube which were large that reduce pressure of gas produced.

Since in experiment 1 we use non-transparent plastic as a digester, in order to show digestion process we conduct another experiment simultaneously without tube.in this the plastic expanded in large which we say it may be a gas.

In experiment 2, no production of gas is produced. The reason that we use for these is the cow dung is old (it is not fresh).

The last two experiments are also didn't give a gas. The reason becomes temperature and mixing.

5.2. Recommendation

Biogas production process is promising, sustainable and alternative form of energy as we see from literature but it need to be studied in detail about freshness of a cow manure, what size of tube is used for what amount of digester.

There must be a place where temperature is constant in the laboratory.

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